

Studies in Fluorinated 1,3-Diketones and Related Compounds—Part XIII* : Synthetic and Spectral Studies of Some New Fluorinated *Tris* Europium 1,3-Diketonates

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A number of new polyfluorinated *tris* europium 1,3-diketonates have been synthesized by treatment of appropriate polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones with europium chloride in methanol. All these compounds have been characterized by their elemental analysis and spectral studies, viz., ir, ^1H nmr and mass. Important absorption peaks are observed in the regions $1620\text{-}1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O), $1540\text{-}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=C), $1000\text{-}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-F).

In ^1H nmr, a sharp singlet at δ (6.2-6.4) ppm due to methine proton (=CH) has been observed.

POLYFLUORINATED 1,3-diketones are indispensable reagents in analytical chemistry and important recent uses are in analysing lunar samples¹, cobalt in vitamin B₁₂² and in the detection of other trace elements in blood, serum and other essential biological materials. Due to their excellent complex forming properties, reagents like theonyltrifluoroacetone (TTA), thiotheonyltrifluoroacetone (STTA), heptafluorobutanoylpivalymethane (FOD) find wide applications in analytical chemistry.

After Hinckley's³ discovery of Eu(DPM)₃, 2 py as nmr shift reagent, a large number of lanthanide 1,3-diketonates have been synthesized as possible nmr shift reagents. The chemical property which permits this application is the Lewis acidity, which the chelates possess, as a consequence of their coordinative unsaturation atmosphere. Chelates of fluorinated 1,3-diketones undergo much stronger interaction with nucleophiles (e.g. alcohols, amines, esters, ethers etc.) than similar non-fluorinated chelates⁴. This is due to the increased acidity⁴ of the fluorinated 1,3-diketones and their increased solubility. In recent years, achiral reagents, like Eu(FOD)₃, have been successfully employed for determination of diastereoisomeric excess of amino acids and other biologically active compounds and a chiral nmr shift reagent, Eu(trifluoroacetyl-d-camphorato)₃, has been utilized to determine the enantiomeric excess in many classes of compounds⁵⁻⁸.

During the last one decade, we have undertaken an extensive programme on the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones^{9,10} and related compounds and have reported the synthesis of new polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones and their metal chelates and some of their structural studies like examination of their quasiaromatic nature and electrophilic substitution reactions in such systems¹¹⁻¹³. We

have also utilized these compounds as reaction intermediates for the synthesis of various bioactive heterocycles¹⁴⁻¹⁹.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer-337 spectrometer. ^1H nmr spectra by a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 in CDCl₃ solution with TMS as an internal standard.

Synthesis of 3,4-difluoroacetophenone : A mixture of 1,2-difluorobenzene (25 g; 0.22 mole) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (61.2 g; 0.46 mole) was taken in a three necked flask (500 ml) fitted with a dropping funnel, mercury sealed stirrer and a reflux condenser. Acetyl chloride (15.6 g; 0.22 mole) was gradually added with stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. The residue was decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid (6N; 150 ml) and extracted with ether, the solvent was removed and 3,4-difluoroacetophenone was dried over magnesium sulphate and distilled at 170°. Synthesis of 2,4,6-trifluoroacetophenone was done in a similar manner. *

Synthesis of polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones : Fluorinated 1,3-diketones were prepared by Claisen condensation reaction of the fluorinated acetophenone with fluorinated esters. Fluorine substituted acetophenone (0.1 mole) was added to an ethereal suspension of sodamide (0.2 mole) with stirring. After half an hour, an ethereal solution of fluorinated ester (0.1 mole) was added dropwise with stirring and refluxed. The reaction mixture was left overnight and then extracted with cold water. The 1,3-diketone was precipitated in the form of its copper(II) chelate by adding a hot solution of cupric acetate. The free 1,3-diketone was regenerated on treatment with 10% sulphuric acid and distilled under reduced pressure.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CHARACTERISTIC DATA OF *Tris* EUROPIUM 1,3-DIKETONATES

Sl. No.	Substituent in Ar	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	C%		H%		F%	
						Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	3,4-DiF	CH ₃	156	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ O ₆ F ₂ Eu	48.45	48.41	2.82	2.81	15.34	15.21
2.	3,4-DiF	CF ₃	183	88	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ F ₁₆ O ₆ Eu	39.78	39.80	1.82	1.80	31.49	31.40
3.	3,4-DiF	C ₂ H ₅	176	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₆ F ₂ Eu	50.44	50.40	3.44	3.42	14.52	14.50
4.	3,4-DiF	C ₆ F ₅	168	70	C ₂₆ H ₁₁ O ₆ F ₁₁ Eu	37.53	37.50	1.14	1.10	37.82	37.80
5.	3,4-DiF	C ₃ F ₇	126	72	C ₂₆ H ₁₁ O ₆ F ₁₇ Eu	35.85	35.82	0.99	1.00	42.57	42.55
6.	2,4,6-TriF	CF ₃	187	85	C ₂₀ H ₆ F ₁₆ O ₆ Eu	37.66	37.62	0.68	0.68	37.55	37.50

Synthesis of tris europium 1,3-diketonates : Europium chloride (0.004 mole) was dissolved in a minimal amount of methanol and added dropwise to a methanolic solution of 1,3-diketonato enolate anion (0.012 mole). The complex was precipitated by slow addition of a ten fold excess of water to the resulting methanolic solution. The precipitated *tris* europium 1,3-diketonates were crystallized from benzene. Finally, the chelates were dried in vacuum, over phosphorus pentaoxide, for 24 hr.

All *tris* europium 1,3-diketonates are recorded in Table 1 with their analytical data.

Results and Discussion

In the ir spectra, the absence of absorption peaks near 1700 cm⁻¹, in all *tris* europium 1,3-diketonates, can be taken as an evidence of all six oxygen atoms of 1,3-diketones being bonded directly to the europium ion. The chemical analysis and M⁺ values in the mass spectra also support their hexacoordination. Other important peaks are at 1620–1540 cm⁻¹ (C=O) stretching mode. 1540–1400 cm⁻¹ (C=C) stretching mode coupled with the C–H in-plane bending mode, 1580–1450 cm⁻¹ (C–F) stretching mode of perfluoroalkyl groups, 1000–850 cm⁻¹ (C–F) deformation mode of perfluoroalkyl groups. The shift in C=O absorption frequency indicates that chelation is stabilized due to the benzenoid resonance effect in which europium back donates its F electrons to the ligand.

In ¹H nmr spectra, disappearance of enolic proton (=C–OH) resonance provides a strong evidence for coordination of 1,3-diketonato anion moiety with europium ion. In all ¹H nmr spectra, a sharp signal is observed at δ(6.2–6.4) ppm which is due to the resonance of the methine proton (=CH)

of the γ-position of the chelated ring. Aromatic protons show sharp signals between δ(6.4–7.9) ppm.

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References

- R. E. SIEVERS *et al.*, *Second Lunar Science Conference*, 1971, 2, 1451.
- W. D. ROSS, W. G. SCRIBNER and R. E. SIEVERS, *Eighth International Symposium on Gas Chromatography*, 1970, 369.
- C. C. HINCKLEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 5160.
- B. FRIBUSH, M. F. RICHARDSON, R. E. SIEVERS and C. S. SPRINGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 6717.
- G. M. WHITESIDES and D. W. LEWIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 6979.
- R. R. FRASER, M. A. PETIT and J. K. SANDERS, *Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 1450.
- G. M. WHITESIDES and D. W. LEWIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 5914.
- F. I. CARROLL and J. T. BLACKWELL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1974, 17, 210 and references therein.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and V. GROVER, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1980, 15, 245.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and S. BHARGAVA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 803.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and V. GROVER, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1979, 13, 261.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and V. GROVER, *IX International Symposium of Fluorine Chem.*, Adignon, France 1979.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and V. GROVER, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1980, 15, 527.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and V. GROVER, *Pharmazie*, 1979, 34, 68.
- K. C. JOSHI and K. DUBRY, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1979, 321, 341.
- K. C. JOSHI and V. N. PATHAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 11, 889.
- K. C. JOSHI and K. DUBRY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 17B, 52.
- K. C. JOSHI and V. K. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 430.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. K. SINGH, D. S. MEHTA, R. C. SHARMA and L. GUPTA, *J. Pharm. Sci., U. S. A.*, 1976, 64, 1248.